

Replication Guide

Image Metadata Analysis to Identify AI-Generated Images

Overview

This guide documents the steps to reproduce the metadata-only classification pipeline using the DeepDetect-2025 dataset.

System Requirements

- OS: Windows 11
- CPU: AMD Ryzen 3 3200G
- RAM: 32 GB
- GPU: NVIDIA GTX 750 Ti (optional)

Software

Python 3.10+; packages: pandas, numpy, scikit-learn, pillow, matplotlib, joblib.

Steps

1) Download dataset

- Kaggle: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/mdwahed/deep-detect-2025>
- Arrange images into two folders: ai/ and real/ under a root directory.

2) Preprocess & split

- Run:
python scripts/preprocess.py --input_dir <root> --out_dir ./data --balance --seed 42
- This creates ./data/train|val|test with ai/ and real/ subfolders.

3) Extract metadata CSVs

- Run:
python scripts/split_data.py --root ./data --out_dir ./metadata

4) Train RandomForest

- Run:
python scripts/train_model.py --train_csv ./metadata/metadata_train.csv --val_csv ./metadata/metadata_val.csv --model_out ./results/rf_model.joblib --log_csv ./logs/training_log.csv

5) Evaluate on test set

- Run:
python scripts/evaluate.py --model ./results/rf_model.joblib --test_csv ./metadata/metadata_test.csv --out_dir ./results

Artifacts

- Results: confusion_matrix.png, roc_curve.png, classification_report.txt
- Logs: training_log.csv, gpu_cpu_utilization.csv